

21NRM05 STASIS

D1: Report on the development and calibration of an implant safety concept in MRI, comprised of sensor-equipped smart medical implants and pTx capable MRI scanners that enable to assess and mitigate in situ RF induced implant heating

Organisation name of the lead participant for the deliverable:

Physikalisch-Technische Bundesanstalt (PTB)

Due date of the deliverable: 30 September 2025

Actual submission date of the deliverable: 30 September 2025

Confidentiality Status: PU - Public, fully open (remember to deposit public deliverables in a trusted repository)

Deliverable Cover Sheet

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European Partnership Co-funded by the European Union

METROLOGY
PARTNERSHIP

The project has received funding from the European Partnership on Metrology, co-financed from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme and by the Participating States.

Glossary

MRI	Magnetic Resonance Imaging
RF	Radiofrequency
SAR	Specific Absorption Rate
DBS	Deep Brain Stimulator
pTx	Parallel Transmission
IPG	Implantable Pulse Generator
AIMD	Active Implantable Medical Device
CP	Circular Polarization
OP	Orthogonal Projection
WC	Worst Case
ADC	Analog to Digital Converter
RMS	Root Mean Square

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1 Summary

Medical implants pose a safety risk for patients in magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) due to radiofrequency induced tissue heating. Current safety practices rely on simulations covering a large variety of exposure scenarios leading to overly conservative RF power limits that reduce image quality and impose a high burden on the clinics. A smart medical implant safety concept can be used for personalized safety assessments and on-the-fly monitoring of RF-induced heating, substantially improving current clinical practice. In this report a simulation-based approach was introduced to develop and build a parallel transmission (pTx) calibration system, which will allow the determination of safety-relevant RF parameters of elongated sensor equipped implants as well as the calibration of the sensor signals including the detection of possible failure scenarios. The main feature of the reported approach is the ability of the pTx based calibration and test hardware to apply a large number (> 1000) of different exposure conditions to the implant and to determine various hazard metrics in relation to $B1+rms$, which complies with the normative requirements of IEC60601-2-33 and ISO/TS 10974.

2 Introduction

When an MR scan is conducted on a patient with an active implantable medical device (AIMD), such as a deep brain stimulator (DBS), the interaction of the RF excitation coil of the MR system with the electrically conductive wires and electrodes of the AIMD can cause substantial increases in RF-induced local SAR and respective tissue heating around the implanted electrodes.^{6,7} The induced local SAR is patient-, implant-, MR- and exam-specific leading to complex simulation models and high uncertainties in the RF safety assessment applied in current standards⁸ to prevent potential tissue damage, e.g. in the brain.⁹ As a consequence SAR limits are substantially reduced in the presence of AIMDs, these limitations affect the imaging, thus, diagnostic performance of the MRI system.

In Deliverable D2 the smart medical implant safety concept was already introduced which is based on personalized measurements rather than generalized simulations¹⁻⁴. Small and inexpensive physical sensors can be attached to the implant electrodes², embedded in the implant casing³ or even unmodified commercial components, such as shown for DBS implants^{15,16}, can be used to

assess the momentary and patient-specific RF hazard. If the MR system and RF coil support more than one independent RF transmission channel, i.e. so-called parallel transmission (pTx), the sensed implant information can be intelligently utilized to substantially mitigate the RF-induced heating without the need to reduce the transmitted RF power and compromise image quality^{2-4,17}.

Suitable pTx-based testing and calibration procedures are essential for the subsequent application of the safety concept described above. Compared to established implant testing procedures for conventional MR systems with a single RF transmission channel, the large number of degrees of freedom in a pTx system leads to significantly greater complexity. On the other hand, pTx-based test systems enable a much larger number of exposure scenarios to be generated in a very short time, e.g., 1000 field configurations in 100 ms. This in turn enables stochastic test procedures and thus both the reliable identification of potentially dangerous situations and a simpler determination of uncertainties in the system. Such pTx-based test systems could therefore also be advantageous for testing implants without built-in sensors and for passive implants. A crucial point here is that the test system can generate traceable electromagnetic field configurations that reflect the typical exposure conditions in 1.5 T or 3 T whole-body MR scanners.

This is achieved in the setup described here by using a body coil with 8 transmit channels, which is geometrically equivalent to the body coil of a conventional 3T MR scanner (see Deliverable D3). This allows the RF exposure to be related to the B1+rms in circularly polarized mode (CP) in accordance with the standard. The traceable determination of B1+rms at the center of the coil in pTx mode is an important result of the project. This allows safety-relevant parameters, such as the temperature rise at the implant tip, to be measured for a variety of exposure conditions in the sense of an end-to-end test. With these data, both implant and MR manufacturers can develop optimization strategies to minimize the risks of RF-induced tissue heating while improving MR imaging performance.

3 Virtual test environment for RF sensor-equipped smart medical implants

In a first step a simulation-based approach was introduced to evaluate the characteristics of a parallel transmission (pTx) calibration and test system, which will allow the determination of safety-relevant RF parameters of elongated sensor equipped implants as well as the calibration of the sensor signals including the detection of possible failure scenarios.

The virtual test environment consists of a series of model calculations that can be used to determine safety-related parameters, such as the point SAR and the local temperature rise as a function of the sensor signal from the smart implant. This allows strategies for calibrating the sensor signals to be developed and possible error scenarios due to interference and signal loss to be identified. This would enable the implant manufacturer to perform a simulation-based risk assessment. The model calculations focused on the use of RMS sensors for pTx mitigation, which proved to be the most affordable option in the previous project.¹⁻⁴

3.1 Simulated sensor signals

The AIMDs primarily considered are neurostimulators (DBS), in which a thin (< 2 mm) electrode measuring 30 cm to 50 cm in length is equipped with a series of electrode pads. The electrodes, which are usually shielded, have corresponding wires inside that connect to the implantable pulse generator (IPG), although the connection to the IPG is typically not completely RF shielded. The RF signals from the tip of the implant conducted via the wires may therefore be affected by RF interference in the area of the IPG and therefore only reflect the conditions at the tip of the implant to a limited extent. In addition, an RF signal is conducted to the IPG from each electrode pad in principle, and the SAR distribution at the various electrode pads may also vary. It is therefore very important to clarify in advance of further developments whether the sensor-based safety concept described in D2 still works in the case of a real implant with significantly higher complexity.

To this end, simulation calculations were carried out on a simplified model of a shielded DBS electrode with 4 internal leads and 4 pads at the tip (see Fig. 1). The IPG, including the connections, was modelled on real AIMDs. The RF excitation is realised via 16 loop coils, each of which was assigned to an RF channel. The FDTD simulation was carried out with an isotropic mesh width of 0.5 mm. From the 4 different sensor signals measured inside the IPG, a linear superposition can

then be determined in the sense of a best fit, which correlates best with the maximum point SAR, e.g. at the location of electrode pad #1 (s. Fig. 2)

Figure 1 Simulated setup with 16 excitation coils and 4 electrode pads.

Figure 2 Correlation of simulated hazard measure (point SAR at electrode #1) with best fit of sensor signal surrogate.

As a result, there is certainly an increased uncertainty in the determination of the point SAR at the electrode pads for the selected model configuration, which is caused by EMF interference. This should be taken into account when designing sensor-equipped smart implants. In any case, the simulation calculations presented allow such effects to be analysed in advance of implant development. However, there are also other measurable variables that can be used as sensor

signals, e.g. changes in impedance between different electrode pads^{15,16}, which are differently sensitive to interference. In the end, the reliability of the considered sensor-equipped smart implant can only be evaluated experimentally with a pTx-based testbed.

3.2 Calibration of sensor signals

For the presented safety concept to be applicable, the recorded sensor signals must be as clearly related as possible to a hazard metric. This allows this hazard metric to be recorded over time before or during an MR examination and risk-minimising measures to be taken. The most relevant hazard metric is the temperature rise at the implant tip. If the temperature rise is limited to 1K or 2K, for example, the risk of possible tissue damage can be estimated and taken into account in the implant manufacturer's risk management.

It is therefore necessary to carry out appropriate simulations of the relationship between the sensor signal and the temperature increase at the implant tip for the simple reference implants considered in this project in order to identify possible systematic sources of error. Furthermore, these simulations also allow the measurement setups for the calibration measurements to be optimised, especially with regard to the positioning of fiber optic temperature probes.

In Fig. 3, for example, it was shown for the reference implant ultimately selected, based on a semi-rigid coaxial cable, that the temperature curves in the proximity of the implant tip can be matched very well with the simulated curves if the measurement position is chosen appropriately.

Figure 3 Simulation of temperature rise (inhouse code²¹). (A) Simulation setup of the coaxial cable tip. (B) Simulated normalized temperature in the plane of the coaxial cable. (C) Normalized temperature difference as a function of time for position A and B compared to a measured curve of position A.

In further simulations, the effect of different tissue parameters on the temperature curves was analysed in comparison to the PVP-based phantom fluid (PVP - polyvinylpyrrolidone) used in the experimental test setup. The comparison considers the tissue types 'white matter', 'grey matter' and 'cerebrospinal fluid' relevant for DBS electrodes. Fig. 4 and Fig. 5 summarise the results for 3T and 7T respectively. These simulations allow conclusions to be drawn about the real conditions in vivo and would have to be carried out by the implant manufacturer in accordance with Tier 3 ISO/TS 10974 anyway.

Figure 3: Simulation results (Sim4Life) of (A-D) RF induced E-fields of a reference implant electrode for a 128MHz RF exposure and different background tissue types and (E-H) corresponding thermal simulations at the electrode. (I) Temperature evolution over an RF heating period of 60s at the location marked with 'x'.

Figure 4: Simulation results (Sim4Life) of (A-D) RF induced E-fields of a reference implant electrode for a 298MHz RF exposure and different background tissue types and (E-H) corresponding thermal simulations at the electrode. (I) Temperature evolution over an RF heating period of 60s at the location marked with 'x'.

3.3 Reference Implant(s)

Two different geometries for the reference implant were investigated, based on the nonmagnetic semi-rigid coaxial cable SUCOFORM_141_CU_FEP (see Fig. 6), a (i) generic collinear 2-electrode lead, and (ii) one with two ring-shaped electrodes. Both electrodes are relatively easy to manufacture, although in the end only the collinear electrode was used for the calibration measurements, while the electrode with the two ring electrodes was examined in detail using simulation.

	Material	Detail	Diameter
Centre conductor	Copper, Silver plated	Wire	0.95 mm
Dielectric	PTFE (Polytetrafluoroethylene)		2.95 mm
Outer conductor	Copper, Tin plated	Tin soaked braid, 100%	3.58 mm
Jacket	FEP (Fluorinated ethylene propylene)	RAL 3020 - rd	4.1 mm +/- 0.1

Figure 6: Specifications of SUCOFORM_141_CU_FEP (Huber+Suhner) .

An RF excitation with a toroidal coil was selected to simulate the reference implant with the two ring electrodes. The advantage of this arrangement is that little power is transmitted into the far field, thereby minimizing background heating. Furthermore, depending on the position of the toroidal coil, various exposure scenarios can be evaluated, which allows for the investigation of systematic errors during calibration and can thus also be included in the measurement uncertainty budget.

Figure 7 Geometry of simulated reference implant with two ring shaped electrodes (right), from simulated temperature distribution (inhouse code²¹) optimum position of FBG probe can be deduced (left).

Fig. 7 shows an example of the geometry of a short implant model used to perform the initial simulations. The simulated temperature distribution was used to determine the optimal position for a fiber optic temperature probe. The temperature-sensitive area of the FBG (Fiber Bragg Grating) temperature probes used is approximately 3 mm to 5 mm long, which is why a position must be found where the temperature gradients along the fiber are as low as possible.

3.4 Reference implant (ii): simulated calibration results

For the simulations with the moving toroidal coil exciter (11 positions), the simulated implant had to be significantly lengthened. This increased the simulation space by a factor of 4, which would have increased the computing time accordingly with the same mesh spacing (125 μm). By adjusting the mesh size along the implant (s. Fig. 8), the computing times (EMF + temperature) could be limited to one day. Another problem was deviations in the simulated characteristic impedance of the cable due to the limited spatial resolution of the model. The problem was circumvented by slightly correcting the dielectric properties of the insulating material. For the sake of simplicity, the temperature of the copper was kept constant in the temperature simulations, i.e., the thermal conductivity of copper (300 ... 400 W/m/K) was not taken into account. Otherwise, the calculation time would have increased by two orders of magnitude. An adaptation of the code, in which only a one-dimensional inclusion of the thermal conductivity of copper was taken into account, was not pursued further.

Figure 8 Geometry of simulated reference implant (ii) with toroidal exciter at different positions.

Each position of the excitation coil results in a specific value for the sensor voltage (determined at the end of the coaxial cable). The dependence on position reflects the transfer function response. A second measured quantity besides the sensor voltage is the peak point SAR in the area around the implant tip. These two measured quantities should correlate well; otherwise, the transfer function approach would be violated. This also applies to the third measured quantity, the temperature increase after a certain time. The simulation calculations performed therefore allow conclusions to be drawn about systematic deviations from the transfer function concept, which must also be taken into account in a real calibration. These deviations are primarily due to the actual geometry and would have to be determined by the implant manufacturer for a specific electrode.

In principle, the peak point SAR can be determined with an E-field probe or an E-field-based SAR probe, whereby a certain spatial averaging takes place. This averaging could also be carried out retrospectively with the simulation data specific to the probe geometry. Another parameter cannot be measured directly, namely the total absorbed power. Only the power originating from the implant is relevant for the evaluation of implant safety, which is why care was taken to ensure that the excitation coil does not generate a background field in the area of the implant tip, if possible. The corresponding results for the reference implant under consideration (ii) are shown in Fig. 9 (square root of peak point SAR vs. sensor signal) and Fig. 10 (peak point SAR vs. absorbed power).

Figure 9 Correlation of the square root of the peak point SAR value with the sensor signal obtained for 11 different positions of the excitation coil.

Figure 10 Correlation between the peak point SAR and the absorbed power for 11 different positions of the excitation coil.

Fig.9 and Fig.10 show that there are slight deviations from the transfer function approach. More relevant for determining the uncertainties in the calibration of the implant sensor are systematic deviations in the measured temperature increase in relation to the sensor signal. Corresponding results are shown in Fig. 11.

With the help of these simulation calculations, the experimentally determined uncertainties in the calibration of the sensor signal can be evaluated in relation to a hazard metric. For the specific geometry of the reference implant (ii) considered here, the systematic uncertainties resulting from the simulations are in the range of 10 to 15 percent and therefore cannot be completely ignored.

Figure 11 Distribution of the temperature rise at 1 V sensor signal for two different points in time, determined for 11 different positions of the excitation coil.

For other geometries, the geometric conditions may lead to other systematic uncertainties. Therefore, the simulations presented in this section need to be adapted by the implant manufacturer to the specific implant geometry in order to be able to estimate the systematic deviations during calibration.

4 New approach for assessing uncertainties for safety-relevant parameters in pTx-based MRI systems

4.1 Experimental background

In two previous 'STASIS' papers^{3,4}, first experimental approaches for the calibration of sensor-based implants were presented. The core of the approach is the generation of randomised pTx voltage vectors with the existing pTx-Safety testbed¹ using a 300MHz (7T) 8-channel pTx coil (s. Fig. 12, 13). This allowed the basic procedure to be demonstrated (see Fig. 12). However, the geometric

conditions in these head coils are not suitable for widely applicable test hardware, which must be based on standard MR systems (1.5T and 3T with body coil).

Figure 12: (A) Correlation of the sensor signal with radial E-field for 1000 random pTx voltage vectors. pTx voltage vectors marked with a diamond were scaled by a factor of 5 and are used in (B). (B) Correlation of squared coaxial sensor signal with temperature rise after of heating for 10 random pTx vectors. Figure taken from Ref.4.

Figure 13: E-field and temperature rise calibration setup used to determine correlation of the sensor signal with radial E-field and with temperature respectively. More details about the setup, field and temperature probes can be found in the corresponding references^{1,3,4}. Figure taken from Ref.3.

4.2 Q-Matrix approach

The crucial point in the development and calibration of an implant safety concept for smart implants equipped with sensors in connection with pTx-capable MR scanners is the implementation of an affordable method for determining uncertainties that adequately takes into account the high number of degrees of freedom resulting from the use of a pTx system. Another point is that MR-compatible implants, i.e., medical devices labelled “MR conditional,” are now mostly labelled with regard to B1+rms, as specified in the latest versions of IEC 60601-2-33 and ISO/TS 10974, especially if MROC (MR Equipment Output Conditioning) is used in the future^{5,8}.

An approach is therefore being sought that will also allow the B1+rms to be determined in the test setup. For this reason alone, only a pTx body coil can be considered as the exposure system for further developments. Such a coil is described in Deliverable D3, of the STASIS project and was used in further work.

We will now consider the following relevant parameters: (i) sensor signal, (ii) E-field/SAR at the tip of the implant, (iii) B1+rms at the center of the body coil, (iv) temperature increase at the tip of the implant, all of which are related to quantities that result from the superposition of the fields generated by the pTx coil.

These quantities can all be represented by a corresponding quadratic form, the so-called Q-matrix \mathbf{Q}_X , where X is related to quantities (i) to (iv). \mathbf{Q}_X is a positive definite Hermitian matrix, meaning it has only positive eigenvalues. \mathbf{Q}_X is defined locally for the measured variables under consideration, i.e., only one eigenvalue should be different from zero, and the associated eigenvector represents the maximum constructive interference of the complex-valued field variables, including the phase angle of the individual RF channels in relation to a selected channel (e.g., channel #1). From measured \mathbf{Q}_X matrices, it is therefore also possible to infer the phase errors of the pTx system without using a phase-sensitive receiving system with the need to have a reference phase available. Hence, only the RMS values need to be recorded, which considerably simplifies measurement data acquisition. This means that even for phase-dependent variables, such as the induced voltage at a pick-up coil (PUC) used for B1 measurement or the voltage at the implant sensor, only RMS values need to be determined. The phase information is provided solely by the coherent pTx system.

Therefore, the Q-Matrix \mathbf{Q}_X contains all relevant information about the pTx system itself, which is why this approach enables end-to-end testing.

Mathematically, this can be summarised as follows:

$$X = \langle \mathbf{u} | \mathbf{Q}_X | \mathbf{u} \rangle \quad (1)$$

For sensor signals that are represented by a complex value U_s , e.g. the RF voltages measured at the implant sensor or the B1 pick-up coil, X would then be equal to $|U_s|^2$. For SAR-related quantities or temperature-related values, X would be e.g. equal to the SAR value or ΔT , respectively. The voltage vector $|\mathbf{u}\rangle$ denotes the complex valued RF excitation signal setting in the pTx MRI system. The rank of \mathbf{Q}_X is determined by the number of independent RF channels N_{chan} .

Based on these properties of \mathbf{Q}_X , the following procedure is used to determine quantities (i) to (iv) and the associated measurement uncertainties.

1. Measurement of \mathbf{Q}_X with a simple pTx sequence:

N_{chan}^2 measurements are required to construct \mathbf{Q}_X as follows:

$$2Q_{X,kl} = \begin{cases} (X_{kl} - X_k - X_l) + j(X_{kl}^\dagger - X_k - X_l) & \text{for } k \neq l \text{ and } k < l \\ (X_{kl} - X_k - X_l) - j(X_{kl}^\dagger - X_k - X_l) & \text{for } k \neq l \text{ and } k > l \\ 2X_k & \text{for } k = l \end{cases}, \quad (2)$$

where X_k is the signal X when only channel k transmits, X_{kl} denotes the signal X when channels k and l transmit simultaneously in phase, and X_{kl}^\dagger the same for a $\pi/2$ phase difference between both channels, while the channels' amplitudes are always identical.

2. Approximate representation of \mathbf{Q}_x by the eigenvector vector $|\mathbf{ev}_x^{\max}\rangle$ at the largest eigenvalue λ_x^{\max} .

\mathbf{Q}_x can be represented as follows:

$$\mathbf{Q}_x = \lambda_x^{\max} |\mathbf{ev}_x^{\max}\rangle\langle\mathbf{ev}_x^{\max}| \quad (3)$$

Then the following results for any pTx voltage vector $|u\rangle$ for the complex valued voltage U_s :

$$U_s = (\lambda_x^{\max})^{0.5} \langle\mathbf{ev}_x^{\max}|u\rangle \quad (4)$$

3. Uncertainties via stochastic approach

A stochastic approach is presented to determine the uncertainties in the system, both the systematic deviations, e.g. those caused by non-linearities, and the random errors (s. Fig.14,15). For example, 1000 random pTx voltage vectors are generated, whereby the maximum amplitude across all transmit channels is limited to a specified value. A sensor value can then be predicted from (4) based on the measured Q-matrix \mathbf{Q}_s . This value can then be compared with the actual measured sensor values, which provides information about the uncertainties in the system. Thus, deviations from the predicted values form a genuine metric for the uncertainties in this multidimensional pTx system.

Figure 14 Scatter plot of the predicted versus measured sensor signal for 1000 randomly selected voltage vectors (7T head coil, s. Fig. 13). When using the eigenvector with the highest eigenvalue for Q_s , the correlation is better and there are fewer outliers.

Figure 15 Scatter plot of the predicted versus measured E-Field at the implant tip for 1000 randomly selected voltage vectors (7T head coil, s. Fig 13). By using the eigenvector with the highest eigenvalue for Q_s , some systematic errors can be avoided, especially for low sensor signals.

Based on this methodology, the final calibration and test setup was developed.

5 Calibration setup for sensor-equipped smart medical implants

The individual components of the setup are described below. The 8ch pTx body coil (Deliverable D3, Fig.16) is driven by the testbed setup from Ref.1 (see also <https://www.opensourceimaging.org/project/ptx-implant-safety-testbed/>). The amplifiers used allow a maximum output power per channel of 20W, whereby the linearity of the amplifiers is satisfactory for output powers of up to 10W. With this setup, up to approx. 100W total power can be applied to the pTx body coil for heating experiments over a longer period of time, which also results in easily measurable temperature increases at the implant tip.

The phantom used is based on the ASTM phantom (Fig.17), but is shorter in order to reduce its mass, which greatly facilitates measurements. In principle, however, the pTx body coil is also suitable for the ASTM phantom. The reference implant is positioned in the phantom, which is filled with a PVP-water mixture³. For this purpose, a mechanical holder was 3D printed to fix the implant in position at the tip and simultaneously accommodate the sensing fiber³ of the FBG temperature instrument (Fig.18). At the end of the coaxial cable used as the reference implant, an SMA connector is attached to the cover, giving the setup the necessary mechanical stability, which is essential for reproducible measurements.

The determination of B_{1+rms} in the centre of the pTx body coil is essential for the end-to-end tests. For this purpose, a mechanical holder for the OSI² pick-up coil was 3D printed (Fig.19), which allows the precise and reproducible fixation of the PUC in two mutually perpendicular positions. This allows the field amplitudes B_{1x} and B_{1y} to be determined, from which B_{1^+} and B_{1^-} are then derived. B_{1^+} or B_{1^-} in CP^+ or CP^- mode is selected as the reference value. The specific direction of rotation of the corresponding B_1 field depends on the orientation of B_0 . Therefore, implants should always be tested in both directions of rotation, as the geometric conditions are not necessarily symmetrical.

Determining the B_1 field components requires in-situ calibration in a TEM cell²², a calculable field source in which the applied voltage is derived from the measurement of the RF power used. This

power is determined using a highly accurate calibrated power measurement head (R&S NRP18TN), which ensures the traceability of the measurements. The FBG sensors used for temperature measurements were also calibrated using a traceable PT100, which means that the determination of temperature-related hazard metrics is also traceable in principle.

As it later became apparent, nonlinearities have a significant impact on the determination of the \mathbf{Q}_x matrix. These nonlinearities can originate from both the RF power amplifiers and the signal acquisition of the sensors. For this reason, the primary measurements were performed with the reference implant connected directly and not with fiber optic transducers or wireless transmission of rectified sensor signals. Nevertheless, the setup can also be used for testing off-the-shelf implants if an E-field sensor or an isotropic SAR probe is placed at the tip of the implant, allowing for sufficiently fast readout. This can then also be used to calibrate a sensor signal with respect to the selected hazard metric¹⁶.

5.1 Final calibration setup/testbed based on 8Ch pTx body coil from DKFZ

The following figures (Fig.16-19) visualize all hardware components used in the calibration procedure.

Figure 16 8-channel pTx body coil used for the calibration and testing setup together with PVP phantom, reference implant inside the phantom, tip holder with temperature sensing fiber (FBG). At the end of the coaxial cable an SMA connector is attached to the cover and connected to the receive system (blue cable). The mechanical holder for the OSI2 pick-up coil is seen in the center of the coil

Figure 17 Detailed view of the phantom with reference implant (red lead), tip holder with temperature sensing fiber), SMA connector and OSI2 pick-up coil.

Figure 18 More detailed views auf the components used, upper row left: overview as seen in Fig. 17, upper row middle: detailed view of tip holder with temperature sensing fiber, upper row right: CAD model of PUC mount for TEM cell, lower row left: CAD model of tip holder, lower row middle: CAD model of holder for the OSI2 pick-up coil, lower row right: detailed view OSI2 pick-up coil with holder.

Figure 19 Components of the TEM calibration setup. Left: PUC in mount for TEM cell, middle: MR-TEM cell²² with PUC inserted, right: used calibrated power measurement probe head (R&S NRP18TN).

5.2 Final calibration setup: influence of nonlinearities

Fig. 20 shows examples of results for the implant sensor at different power levels. The attenuation level $att=0.3$ corresponds to a maximum forward power of approximately 1W per channel, whereby it should be noted that this power is not measured directly at the coil because, in the sense of an end-to-end test, all measured quantities are related to the $B1+rms$ at the center of the coil. CP+ and CP- modes are particularly highlighted pTx voltage vectors, whereby the implant sensor signal is very different for both modes. This emphasizes that tests must be performed in both modes. The influence of the nonlinearities of the RF power amplifiers is evident; the corresponding uncertainties (s. Fig. 21) would have to be taken into account in a real pTx system.

Figure 20 Final calibration setup: results for the reference implant sensor signal for different power levels.

Figure 21 Uncertainties determined from the measurements described in Fig. 20. Due to increasing nonlinearities at higher power levels, the uncertainties increase dramatically.

5.3 Final calibration setup: results of sensor calibration

In the next step, 20 excitation vectors with increasing sensor signals were selected so that the expected temperature changes are distributed as evenly as possible. Fig. 22 shows the results of the calibration for a heating periode of 60 s, so that the corresponding value of the temperature increase can be deduced from each sensor signal. The corresponding uncertainties must then be taken into account in the final uncertainty budget, which in turn is a task for the implant manufacturer in connection with risk management.

Figure 22 Measured temperature increase after 60 seconds of heating compared to the expected sensor response from the measured Q_S matrix.

5.4 Final Calibration setup: sensor output vs B1+rms

In the following, the sensor signals for the 1000 random pTx voltage vectors, determined from the measured Q_S matrix, were first compared with the corresponding values of B1+ and B1- (Fig. 23). Both values can be used as B1+rms depending on the orientation of the B_0 field.

In addition, the results for the OP mode^{2,3} were plotted, i.e. pTx voltage vectors that are perpendicular to $|\mathbf{e}_{v_x^{\max}}\rangle$ and thus should not generate a sensor signal and therefore no heating at the implant tip. The results are consistent with the simulations from Ref. 4 and demonstrate the applicability of the described concept for future implant test strategies.

Figure 23 Sensor signals for 1000 random pTx voltage vectors compared with the corresponding values of B1+ and B1-. In addition, results for the OP mode^{2,3} were plotted, i.e. pTx voltage vectors that are perpendicular to $\langle ev_{\chi}^{max} \rangle$ and thus should not generate a sensor signal.

Figure 24 Calibrated temperature increase after 60 seconds of heating for 1000 random pTx voltage vectors compared with the corresponding values of B1+. The figure shows that there are a large number of pTx voltage vectors that have both a high B1+rms and a low implant heating level.

Finally, Fig. 24 shows the key result of the calibration procedure developed for sensor-based smart AIMDs in pTx-capable MR systems. In accordance with Fig. 23, the temperature rise at the implant tip is now compared with the B1+rms values at the center of the coil. Among other things, this shows that there are a large number of pTx voltage vectors that have both a high B1+rms and a low implant heating level. This testing methodology using the open source hardware from Deliverable D3 is therefore a key result and will in future allow not only sensor-based smart implants to be tested, but in principle implants of all kinds, whereby the ability to generate a large number of field configurations could increase the reliability of the test results.

6 Summary and conclusions

An implant safety concept for MRI was developed, which makes it possible for sensor-equipped smart medical implants and pTx-capable MRI scanners to evaluate the RF-induced implant heating in situ and mitigate it accordingly. In addition, suitable pTx-based testing and calibration procedures and corresponding hardware were developed, which are essential for the subsequent application of this safety concept. Compared to established implant testing methods for conventional MR systems with a single RF transmission channel, the pTx-based testing system described above can run through a very large number of exposure scenarios in a very short time, e.g., 1000 field configurations in 100 ms. This in turn enabled the development of a stochastic test procedure that allows both the reliable identification of potentially hazardous situations and a simpler determination of uncertainties in the system. Such pTx-based test systems could therefore also be advantageous for testing implants without built-in sensors and for passive implants. Crucially, the test system must be able to generate reproducible electromagnetic field configurations that reflect the typical exposure conditions in 1.5 T or 3 T whole-body MR scanners.

First, a simulation-based approach was presented to evaluate the properties of a pTx-based calibration and test system that allows the determination of safety-relevant RF parameters of

elongated, sensor-equipped implants and the calibration of sensor signals, including the detection of possible failure scenarios.

For a reference implant based on a semi-rigid coaxial cable, it was shown that the temperature evolution near the tip of the implant can match simulated curves very well if the measurement position is chosen appropriately.

In addition, two different geometries for the reference implant were investigated, both of which are based on the non-magnetic semi-rigid coaxial cable SUCOFORM_141_CU_FEP, namely a generic collinear 2-electrode cable and one with two ring-shaped electrodes. Both reference implants are relatively easy to manufacture, although ultimately only the collinear electrode was used for the calibration measurements, while the electrode with the two ring electrodes was analysed in more detail using simulation.

With the help of these simulations, the experimentally determined uncertainties in the calibration of the sensor signal could be evaluated in relation to a hazard metric. For the specific geometry of the reference implant with two ring-shaped electrodes considered here, the systematic uncertainties resulting from the simulations are in the range of 10 to 15 per cent and can therefore not be neglected in the overall budget.

A new approach for the determination of uncertainties for safety-relevant parameters in pTx-based MRI systems was developed, which allows the reference to B1+rms and thus in principle enables the labelling of the implant as "MR conditional" according to the latest versions of IEC 60601-2-33 and ISO/TS 10974, especially when using MROC (MR Equipment Output Conditioning).

With the stochastic approach presented, the uncertainties in the system, both the systematic deviations, e.g. due to non-linearities, and the random errors can be determined.

A test system is presented that uses a pTx body coil with 8 transmission channels, which geometrically corresponds to the body coil of a conventional 3T MR scanner. This allows the RF exposure to be related to the B1+rms in circularly polarised mode (CP) in accordance with standards. The traceable determination of B1+rms in the centre of the coil in pTx mode is also an important result of the project. This allows safety-relevant parameters, such as the temperature rise at the implant tip, to be measured for various exposure conditions in the sense of an end-to-end test. With

this data, both implant and MR manufacturers can develop optimisation strategies to minimise the risks of RF-induced tissue heating while improving MR imaging performance.

In summary, the aims of the STASIS project deliverable have been successfully achieved, fulfilling Objective 1 of the project.

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8 Related other Deliverables

- D2: Report on the technical specifications and the communication workflow for sensor-equipped smart medical implants within an MRI scanner, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15502183>
- D3: Report on the development of open-source reference hardware (RF coil, exciter, modulators, RF power amplifier) and open-source control software, including traceable measurement procedures that allow testing of implants under pTx MR conditions